

Molybdenum: Part III.* Dioxo Molybdenum (VI) Complexes with Hydroxamic Acids

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Molybdates and hydroxamic acids have been shown to react in aqueous medium at around pH 3.0 to furnish yellow to pale yellow dioxo-bishydroxamate molybdenum (VI) as sparingly soluble products. Absorption spectra and diamagnetism identify these as molybdenum (VI) derivatives. Solution studies at pH 3.0 and around pH 7.0 again indicate 1:2 metal ligand ratio in dilute solution. The complexes have been re-crystallised unchanged from alcohols, thus indicating that no esterification of the ligand units occurs.

The infra red spectra of the bis-benzohydroxamate dioxomolybdenum (VI) has been studied and compared to that of the free reagent acid and an oxo-vanadium (IV) chelate.

Complexes of hexavalent molybdenum are little known¹. Most of the complexes known are anionic with halogen and/or oxygen as the donor centre such as $[\text{MoOF}_6]^{2-}$, $[\text{MoO}_2\text{F}_4]^{2-}$, $[\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_4]^{2-}$ etc. In addition to the above, neutral complexes such as $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2]$, (acacH=acetylacetonone); $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{oxin})_2]$ (oxinH=8-hydroxyquinoline) etc. are known in a few limited cases. The situation has remained such for want of a suitable and readily available source of molybdenum(VI). The simplest available source is a molybdate salt but with such a starting material, it is quite difficult to sever the strong molybdenum-oxygen bonds so as to initiate complexation. As a result only a few complexes are known, which have been obtained by operating in aqueous solution under varied pH conditions. Thus 8-hydroxyquinoline², cystein³, benzoyl, phenyl hydroxylamine⁴, EDTA⁵, α -carboxy- β -methyl tropolone⁶; 8-hydroxyquinoline 5-sulphonic acid⁷ and oxalic acid⁸ are few known ligands which have yielded complexes of hexavalent molybdenum either in solid crystalline state or in solution. All these complexes are invariably of the type $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{R})_2]$, where RH is a monobasic bidentate ligand. One other source of molybdenum(VI), which has been examined of late is dioxodichloro molybdenum(VI). This certainly has the advantage over the molybdates in solution, as in this case the weak molybdenum-chlorine bonds need only be broken. Reactions of this starting material with diethylenetriamine⁹, dimethyl sulphoxide¹⁰, triphenyl phosphine oxide¹¹, triphenylarsine oxide¹¹, acetylacetonone¹¹, amides and histidine¹² have been studied and reported. In a very special case, it has been

* Part II. see this *Journal*, No. 8, 1967.

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observed that MoOCl_2 , even extracts oxygen from dimethyl sulfoxide to furnish a complex of dioxodichloro molybdenum(VI)¹⁰.

Viewed in the above context, we observed that aromatic hydroxamic acids, with reactive grouping CONHOH do react with molybdates in aqueous solutions to furnish yellow coloured complexes. Prior to this present study, the reactions between a few hydroxamic acids and molybdate ion have been investigated but with the interest of spectrophotometric analyses alone¹¹. We have, however investigated the system from the standpoint of complex formation. The methods of preparation and isolation of solid complexes, nature of the complexes in dilute solution at more than one pH, absorption spectra as also the reactions of the complexes with alcohols form the subject matter of this communication. Besides, the infrared spectra of the benzohydroxamate complex has also been examined and the nature of the attachment of the metal to the ligand studied.

The aromatic hydroxamic acids studied include benzohydroxamic acid, O-Chloro-; P-chloro-; O-nitro-; O-hydroxy-benzo-hydroxamic acid; phenyl acet hydroxamic acid and hexa-hydrobenzo-hydroxamic acids. In general, it was observed that a molybdate solution developed a strong yellow colour with any of these hydroxamic acids around pH 6.7. The solution, when treated with acids to a pH around 3.0 precipitates a yellow to pale yellow coloured crystalline product.

This insoluble product was found to be dioxo-bis-hydroxamate molybdenum(VI). Conductance measurements on these materials in methanol gave, as expected, non-electrolyte values.

TABLE I
Conductance Measurements

[Temp = 35°C; Concentration = 0.001M; Solvent = Methanol (G.R.).

Compound	Colour	Molar Conductance (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)
1. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Yellow	10.14
2. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	"	7.55
3. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	"	4.41
4. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{ClN})_2]$	"	5.99
5. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{ClN})_2]$	"	5.20
6. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N}_2)_2]$	"	4.38
7. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	"	9.18
8. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Colourless	3.08

Besides, we also refluxed some of these complexes in various alcohols and obtained glistening materials, which also provided the same analytical figures as for the complexes obtained from aqueous medium. The melting points of the two series of preparations were identical. This study was undertaken because the ligands admit of a hydroxy-oxime structure, in which case there is a possibility of the unreacted hydroxy groups to get esterified. If this would have happened, the analytical figures must have widely differed particularly in the case of a heavy alcohol such as n-butanol nor has there been any notable change in the melting point of the two preparations. These observations are significant in view of a

reaction that the oxo-hydroxo-bis-hydroxamate vanadium(V) undergo with alcohols resulting in the formation of oxo-alkoxo-bis-hydroxamate vanadium(V) with a large body of aromatic hydroxamic acids¹⁴. The failure of any reaction of the present molybdenyl complexes with alcohols indicate the absence of any OH group attached to the molybdenum and further that it is not quite easy to esterify the ligands. Besides the infrared spectra of both the preparations have been almost superimposable. For comparison, we have taken the spectra of the free benzo-hydroxamic acid, its potassium salt, the bis-benzohydroxamate oxo-vanadium(IV) and that of the dioxo-molybdenum bis benzohydroxamate as precipitated from aqueous solution at pH 3 and as recrystallised from butanol. The spectra of the free acid and its potassium salt have already been reported in the literature¹⁵. We have had the spectra retaken for a good comparison. As was observed in our Laboratory with the vanadium complexes we observed again that the absorption bands around 1300cm^{-1} , 1600cm^{-1} and around $3,175-3,300\text{cm}^{-1}$, are the ones, which have suffered the most on complexation. That the hydroxamic acid had the hydroxamide structure rather than the hydroxy-oxime structure has already been discussed from the IR spectra of the free acid and its potassium salt. Based on the hydroxamide structure the carbonyl oxygen will serve as a donor centre in the metal chelates and the following resonating structures for the coordinating ligand may be visualised:

TABLE II

Infrared spectra (cm^{-1}).

BH ₂	KRH	[VO(RH) ₂]	[MoO ₂ (RH) ₂] (recrystallised from n-butanol).	[MoO ₂ (RH) ₂] (aqueous medium)
710	696	699	700	700
805	792	790	800	795
910	896	916	900	900
		974	940	935
		993		
1030	1023	1023	1040	1030
1052	1044		1070	1070
1170	1157	1150	1170	1160
1320	1307	1346	1360	1360
1450	1444	1444	1460	1450
	1487	1479		1495
1500	1523	1513	1500	
1580			1540	1535
1660	1611	1595	1600	1600
2810				
3070		3095	3080	3080
3300	3175			

14. Dutta and Lahiry, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 860; 1963, 40, 53.15. Umova and Voroshin, *Doklady, Akad. Nauk, SSSR*, 1957, 113, 1306; Mathis, *Compt. rend.*, 1951, 232, 505; Dutta and Lahiry, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 860; 1963, 40, 53.

As a consequence, there will be electron withdrawal from the carbonyl group which in turn will increase the electron density in the CN bond. Therefore, a lowering of carbonyl frequency and an increase of CN bond are expected. The carbonyl bond at 1660cm^{-1} in our free reagent is shifted to 1695cm^{-1} in the vanadium complex and to 1600cm^{-1} to molybdenum complexes. The CN bond frequency at 1320cm^{-1} in the free reagent goes over to 1346cm^{-1} in the vanadium complex and to 1360cm^{-1} in the molybdenum chelates.

Besides the OH band in the free acid $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \parallel \\ \text{C} \\ | \\ \text{NH} - \text{OH} \end{array}$ at 2810cm^{-1} is altogether missing in the potassium salts and in the complexes. The NH frequency at 3300cm^{-1} and the OH stretch at 3070cm^{-1} in the free acid are changed to one band at 3175cm^{-1} in the potassium salt and at 3095cm^{-1} in Vanadium complex and at 3080cm^{-1} in Molybdenum complexes. Thus the nature of attachment of the ligand to Vanadium(IV) and Molybdenum(VI) are basically the same. Further the Molybdenum chelate reveals a strong band around $935-940\text{cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of MoO_4^{++} species¹⁶. Any oxy-metal cation involving a single oxygen-metal bond absorbs at considerably higher frequency around $970-980\text{cm}^{-1}$.¹⁷

The visible absorption spectra of all the complexes were run in ethanol. In all cases yellow solutions were formed and the spectra revealed a high intensity band in the ultra violet region. There was no indication of any band in the usual ligand field region. Thus as expected, dioxo dihydroxamato Molybdenum(VI), shows bands arising out of charge transfer from the ligands to Molybdenum only.

In dilute solution, composition of the complexes at two different pH regions was determined by Job's method of continuous variation of equimolar solution (Figs. I & II).

FIG. I. Job's curve for molybdenyl O-chlorobenzohydroxamate Complex at pH 3.0 and at pH 7.5.

FIG. II. Job's curve for molybdenyl benzohydroxamate Complex at pH 3.0 and at pH 7.5.

At both the pH, the same metal-ligand empirical ratio, namely, 1:2, was indicated. A plot of optical density against varying pH at several wave lengths of light provide curves of

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17. Barraclough, Lewis and Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3552.

18. Bhatt, *Org. Syn. Coll.*, Vol II, p.67, Dutta and Ghosh, *this Journal*, (in Press)

similar nature, indicating the formation of a single complex in solution (Fig. IV). The complex species at around pH 3.0 can be easily extracted out by immiscible, higher alcohols, whereas that around pH 7.0 was very poorly extracted. This probably indicated that at lower pH the complex remains primarily as an undissociated, non-electrolyte complex and at around pH 7.0 as an anion through the operation of the following structures:

FIG. III. Absorption spectra of dioxo molybdenyl bishydroxamate Complexes in ethanol.

- (a) $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$
 (b) $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{ClN})_2]$
 (c) $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)_2]$
 (d) $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$

FIG. IV. Variation of optical density against pH at different wave lengths. System: Molybdate ion and excess benzo-hydroxamic acid.

All the complexes have given rise to diamagnetic values, as one expects for Molybdenum(VI) complexes with no electrons available in the d-orbitals.

EXPERIMENTAL

The following hydroxamic acids were used to prepare compounds of Mo (VI): (a) Benzo-, (b) Salicyl-, (c) Phenylacet-, (d) P-Anisyl-, (e) P-introbenzo-, (f) m-nitrobenzo-, (g) O-chlorobenzo-, (h) P-chlorobenzo- and (i) Hexahydro-benzohydroxamic acids. Synthesis and reactions of hexahydrobenzohydroxamic acid will be reported in a separate communication.

Bishydroxamato-dioxo Molybdenum(VI) (yellow)—An aqueous solution of ammonium paramolybdate (1 mole) and aqueous solution of the hydroxamic acid (2.5 moles) were mixed when a deep yellow solution was produced. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 2.5 to 3.5 by adding drop by drop (1:1) HCl when a yellow crystalline compound separated.

The yellow compound was allowed to stand for few minutes, filtered, washed several times with distilled water and dried over CaCl_2 .

All the compounds prepared were bright yellow to light yellow except bisphenylacet hydroxamate dioxo-Molybdenum(VI) which was colourless.

Some of the dioxo bis-hydroxamate-Molybdenum(VI) compounds were prepared from aqueous medium, suaked perfectly dry and refluxed with either n-butanol or isopropanol (10 ml, B.D.H.) for more than an hour. The compounds isolated in every case formed beautiful, yellow shining crystals. The isolation of these compounds from lower alcohols such as ethanol were not possible because of the formation of gummy mass.

The analytical results are given below:

Compound	% Mo	% N	Decomposition temp. (°C)
1. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	F: 24.5 (23.8) R: 24.0	F: 6.7 (6.7) R: 7.0	189-90 (190-91)
2. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	F: 22.2 (21.8) R: 22.1	F: 6.1 (6.4) R: 6.4	166-67 (164-65)
3. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	F: 22.6 R: 22.3	F: 6.6 R: 6.5	203-204
4. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)_2]$	F: 19.5 R: 19.5	F: 11.4 R: 11.7	218-219
5. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)_2]$	F: 20.0 R: 19.5	F: 11.6 R: 11.7	196-97
6. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{ClN})_2]$	F: 21.00 (20.4) R: 20.29	F: 6.0 (5.65) R: 5.9	187-88 (188-89)
7. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{ClN})_2]$	F: 20.99 R: 20.29	F: 5.95 R: 5.9	187-88
8. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	F: 23.0 R: 22.88	F: 7.0 R: 6.8	208-10
9. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	F: 20.6(20.6) R: 20.8	F: 6.06 (6.06) R: 6.08	190-92 (193-94)

($\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{NH}$ - Benzohydroxamic acid; $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{NH}$ = Salicyl hydroxamic acid; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{NH}$ = Phenyl acet hydroxamic acid; $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}$ = P-nitro benzo hydroxamic acid; $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}$ = m-nitrobenzo hydroxamic acid; $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{ClNH}$ = P-chlorobenzohydroxamic acid; $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{ClNH}$ = O-chlorobenzohydroxamic acid; $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{NH}$ = Hexa hydro benzohydroxamic acid and $\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{NH}$ = P-anisylhydroxamic acid).

Analytical results in parentheses are for those complexes which have been recrystallised unchanged from n-butanol or isopropanol. Other figures stand for complexes precipitated from aqueous medium around pH 3.0.

Composition studies in solution: The usual Job's method was followed. Equimolar solution of Molybdate (.001M) and of the respective hydroxamic acid (.001M) were prepared. Continued variations were made keeping the total volume (reagent + metal) constant (2^o ml.).

TABLE III
Molar extinction coefficient (in ethanol)

Compound	Colour	Wavelength	
1. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Yellow	330	2,860
2. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{ClN})_2]$	"	330	1,500
3. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)_2]$	"	330	8,000
4. $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Colourless	330	124

The pH was then adjusted as desired and finally volume made upto 25ml. Optical density was then read in a Uvispeck Spectrophotometer in 1cm cells at selected wavelengths. Corrections for no reaction was made and the corrected optical density (Fig. I, Fig. II.) was plotted against mole fraction of the reagent $[R/(M+R)]$.

Analytical methods—Molybdenum content was determined either by decomposing the complexes with equal values of Conc. H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 and then adjusting the suitable pH with NaOH solution, precipitating with Oxine, weighing as $[MoO_3(oxine)_2]$, or by decomposing the complex with alkali—hydrogen peroxide and then precipitating as $[MoO_3(oxine)_2]$. Nitrogen was estimated by combustion technique.

Magnetic measurements—The magnetic susceptibilities were determined by the Gouy method using a semimicro Mettler Balance for measuring the difference in weight with a field strength of 8.57×10^5 gauss. The visible spectra were recorded on a Hilger Spectrophotometer using 1cm. cell. The Infrared spectra were scanned on a Beckmann spectrophotometer model IR -4 using NaCl prism.

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